

Mapping seabird and marine biodiversity sensitivity to marine wind farm expansion in Portugal

João L. Guilherme, Beatriz Morais, Hany Alonso, Joana Andrade, Ana Almeida, Nuno Barros, and Maria P. Dias

November 2023

Partnership:

Supported by:

Mapping seabird and marine biodiversity sensitivity to marine wind farm expansion in Portugal

João L. Guilherme¹, Beatriz Morais², Hany Alonso³, Joana Andrade³, Ana Almeida³, Nuno Barros³ & Maria P. Dias⁴

¹Independent researcher, 34090 Montpellier, France

²Independent researcher, 2580-654 Alenquer, Portugal

³Sociedade Portuguesa para o Estudo das Aves, Av. Almirante Gago Coutinho, 46A 1700-031 Lisboa, Portugal (www.spea.pt)

⁴cE3c – Centre for Ecology, Evolution and Environmental Changes & CHANGE – Global Change and Sustainability Institute, Department of Animal Biology, Faculty of Sciences of the University of Lisbon, Campo Grande, 1749-016 Lisboa, Portugal

Email: joaoguilherme@gmail.com

Report available at: https://african-eurasian-migrants.shinyapps.io/Seabird_sensitivity_wind_farms/

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors would like to thank Fundação Oceano Azul (<https://www.oceanoazulfoundation.org/>) for supporting this study. The data compiled in this study were originally collected by hundreds of researchers, professional ornithologists, and citizen scientists, whom the authors would like to thank for the dedication and long hours spent in the field.

Citation: Guilherme JL, Morais B, Alonso H, Andrade J, Almeida A, Barros N & Dias MP (2023). Mapping seabird and marine biodiversity sensitivity to marine wind farm expansion in Portugal | Mapeamento da sensibilidade das aves marinhas à energia eólica no mar em Portugal (Version 1). Sociedade Portuguesa para o Estudo das Aves (SPEA). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10045918>

ABSTRACT

The expansion of renewable energy is key for the energy transition and independence of the European Union countries. In 2023, the Portuguese government has proposed priority sites for the construction of new marine wind farms along the Portuguese mainland coast (up to 65 km offshore). Marine (offshore) wind farms may conflict with the sustainable management and conservation of marine resources; it is therefore a priority to assess which areas are most sensitive for marine biodiversity in light of the expected impacts of this type of structures. Seabirds play an important role in marine trophic chains, are a very threatened group, and may suffer significant impacts during construction and operation of marine wind farms, including direct mortality by collision and displacement due to disturbance or to the barrier effect that wind farms pose to local movements and migration. Consequently, seabirds are a key group to consider when assessing the sensitivity of marine biodiversity to the construction of offshore wind farms. Here, we identify the areas along the Portuguese mainland coast where wind energy expansion may be most critical for the conservation of seabirds. We analysed the sensitivity and seasonal distribution of 34 seabird species that regularly occur along the Portuguese mainland coast (up to 65 km offshore), using a refined version of the methodology most commonly used for similar assessments in other European countries. We estimated sensitivity of each species based on factors associated with collision vulnerability, displacement vulnerability, and conservation status at national and international levels. The seasonal distribution of each species was based on previous published work. We found that three sites – Viana do Castelo North, Viana do Castelo South, and Ericeira – overlap with areas of high sensitivity for seabirds, and therefore should be reconsidered and redesigned. In addition, the Ericeira site is adjacent to two Special Protection Areas and in the vicinity of the only colony of Cory's shearwater and Band-rumped storm-petrel on the mainland coast (Ilhas Berlengas), and coincides with foraging areas used by Cory's shearwaters during the breeding season. Also noteworthy to highlight are the proximity of the Viana do Castelo North site to another wind farm site in Spain (which has already been approved), and the possible overlap of the Sines site with migratory routes of seabirds. This report also includes a preliminary analysis of the sensitivity of shorebirds and marine mammals to offshore wind farms, revealing that the proposed sites do not overlap with areas particularly important for these groups; however, the lack of data for these groups limited the analyses and conclusions. This is the first study to identify the areas of highest sensitivity of seabirds to offshore wind farm expansion in Portugal, providing a benchmark for future analysis and a valuable contribution to inform ongoing policy decision making. Nevertheless, we highlight the importance of filling existing knowledge gaps for some species, in particular, the need for a more detailed understanding of the migratory routes of many species of seabirds and shorebirds, and the distribution of marine mammals.

CONTENTS

INTRODUCTION.....	5
RESULTS AND DISCUSSION.....	8
1. Seabird sensitivity to marine wind farms.....	8
2. Areas of importance for other marine biodiversity.....	12
2.1. Areas at sea important for shorebirds.....	12
2.2. Areas of importance for marine mammals.....	13
3. Risk at the sites proposed for marine wind farm construction.....	14
CONCLUSIONS.....	17
METHODS.....	19
1. Seabird sensitivity to marine wind farms.....	19
1.1. Species-density distribution maps.....	19
1.2. Seabird Species Sensitivity Index (SSI).....	21
1.2.1. Collision Vulnerability (CV).....	22
1.2.2. Displacement Vulnerability (DV).....	23
1.2.3. Conservation Score (CS).....	25
1.3. Mapping seabird sensitivity to marine wind farms.....	25
2. Areas of importance for other marine biodiversity.....	26
2.1. Areas at sea important for shorebirds.....	26
2.2. Areas of importance for marine mammals.....	26
3. Risk at the sites proposed for marine wind farm construction.....	27
3.1. Proposed sites and marine biodiversity conservation instruments.....	27
4. Software.....	28
REFERENCES.....	29
ANNEX I.....	34

INTRODUCTION

The expansion of renewable energy is key for the energy transition and independence of the European Union countries (Gielen et al., 2019). The implementation of marine (offshore) wind farms, which is deemed strategic within EU's "Blue Economy" framework (European Commission, 2021), has grown considerably in the last decade along the northern European coast (e.g., Baltic and North Sea) and a boom in these infrastructures is expected to take place along Europe's entire Atlantic and Mediterranean coasts (European Parliament, 2021). Accordingly, in 2013 the Portuguese government proposed the Allocation Plan for Renewable Energy Exploitation (PAER), which proposes six priority sites for concessions for the construction of new wind farms along the mainland coast (DGRM, 2023a) (Figure 1). However, the construction, operation, and maintenance of new wind farms imposes additional pressure on marine biodiversity, which is already under great strain (Halpern et al., 2015; Dias et al., 2019). The construction of new marine wind farms may thus conflict with the sustainable management and conservation of marine resources (Gill, 2005), particularly of seabirds (Garthe & Hüppop, 2004; Furness et al., 2013), but also of other biodiversity, such as shorebirds (or waders; Schwemmer et al., 2023) and marine mammals (Thompson et al., 2010). Therefore, it is a priority to assess which areas are most sensitive for marine biodiversity and to what extent the sites proposed in the PAER overlap with these areas.

Despite the key role they play in marine, coastal, and terrestrial ecosystems (Plazas-Jiménez & Cianciaruso, 2020; Signa et al., 2021), seabirds have to deal with an increasingly crowded and dangerous ocean (Dias et al., 2019). Human pressures, including bycatch, overfishing, disease, and introduced predators into breeding colonies, have resulted in seabirds being one of the most threatened animal groups (Dias et al., 2019), with the expansion of offshore wind farms posing an additional worrying threat for these birds (Halpern et al., 2015; Dias et al., 2019). Several studies have reported negative impacts from offshore wind farms on different seabirds. These are mainly concerned with direct mortality due to collisions with turbines and infrastructure, displacement – and thus loss of habitat – due to avoidance of wind farms and increased disturbance by vessels and helicopters (during construction and maintenance), and barrier effect to local movements (e.g., between breeding colonies and foraging areas) as well as to migratory routes (e.g., Masden et al., 2009; Dierschke et al., 2016; Garthe et al., 2017, 2023; Cook et al., 2018; Peschko et al., 2020). For shorebirds, which often fly over the sea while on migration and when moving between coastal wetlands, interactions with offshore wind farms can result in direct mortality by collision, even when these are placed several kilometres offshore (Watts et al., 2022; Schwemmer et al., 2023). As for marine mammals, habitat displacement, particularly due the noise generated during construction, has been reported as an important threat (Carstensen et al., 2006).

Sensitivity mapping provides a simple framework to identify areas of particular environmental sensitivity to potential threats, which is critical to the sustainable use of natural resources. Sensitivity mapping has been used to identify areas of sensitivity of seabirds to offshore wind farms in different regions (e.g., Gulf of Biscay: Certain et al., 2015; North Sea: Garthe & Hüppop, 2004; England: Bradbury et al., 2014; India, Nepal, Thailand, and Vietnam: Serratos & Allinson, 2022; US North-East Pacific: Kelsey et al., 2018). Briefly, sensitivity mapping integrates species' distribution maps with a sensitivity index, which is built by taking into account species-specific ecological and behavioural factors related to their vulnerability to colliding with wind farm structures, their vulnerability to

displacement due to disturbance by wind farms, and their conservation status. These maps can thus help inform decision-making in order to conciliate marine wind farm profitability and conservation of marine biodiversity.

Proposed sites for marine wind farm construction

Figure 1: Proposed sites for marine wind farm expansion and key marine areas for biodiversity conservation.

White polygons are the boundaries of the six priority sites proposed in the Allocation Plan for Renewable Energy Exploitation (PAER) for marine wind farm expansion (the Aguçadora site is a pilot marine wind farm in operation since 2020). Wind farm sites are shown in context with the boundaries of the main policy instruments of marine biodiversity management and conservation, including Protected Areas (PA), Special Protection Areas (SPA), Sites of Community Importance (SCI), as well as globally Important Bird & Biodiversity Areas (IBA) (details in Table 5). The grey polygon represents a site already approved for wind farm construction in Spanish waters.

Portugal hosts a great diversity of seabirds and shorebirds, including species breeding in coastal wetlands and in islands (e.g., ‘Ilhas Berlengas’ SPA; Ilhas Berlengas Standard Data Form¹), several migratory species from colonies spread across North Atlantic countries that depend on the waters under Portuguese jurisdiction to migrate safely twice a year, and species that find the optimal conditions along the Portuguese coast to spend the non-breeding season (Cтры et al., 2010). Indeed, at-sea and land-based surveys have confirmed the regular presence of around 70 marine and coastal species (Meirinho et al., 2014) and documented movements involving tens of thousands of birds a day during migrations (Elmberg et al., 2020). For species such as the Critically Endangered Balearic shearwater, Portuguese coastal waters are of major importance, hosting large percentages of their world’s populations (Cтры et al., 2010; Meirinho et al., 2014). For marine mammals, 23 species of cetaceans are known to occur along the Portuguese mainland coastal waters (Vingada et al., 2011), although the existing information on their occurrence in Portugal is still sparse and incomplete (Vingada et al., 2011). Considering that seabirds,

¹ Ilhas Berlengas SPA PTZPE0009 Standard Data Form: <https://natura2000.eea.europa.eu/natura2000/SDF.aspx?site=PTZPE0009>

shorebirds, and cetaceans are among the animals most threatened by growing anthropogenic pressures (Sutherland et al., 2012; Dias et al., 2019; Chen et al., 2022), the international importance of Portuguese waters for these species puts into perspective the role – and thus the responsibility – of the Portuguese government to ensure that the proposed sites in the PAER have the least possible impact on these species and the marine ecosystem.

Here, we identify the areas along the Portuguese mainland coast where wind energy expansion may be most critical for the conservation of marine biodiversity, focusing mostly on seabirds but considering also shorebirds and marine mammals. We mapped the sensitivity of seabirds to offshore wind farms based on the distribution of 34 species that regularly occur along the Portuguese mainland coast, using a refined version of the methodology most commonly used for similar assessments in other countries. For each species, we considered the probability of occurrence in each season across the year (using the distribution maps in the Atlas of Marine Birds of Portugal; Meirinho et al., 2014), and its sensitivity to offshore wind farms. We estimated sensitivity of each species based on factors associated with collision vulnerability, disturbance vulnerability, and conservation status at national and international levels. To represent the importance of Portuguese waters for shorebirds and marine mammals, we adopted a more simplistic methodology since the lack of data for these groups precluded a similar approach to that used for seabirds.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Seabird sensitivity to marine wind farms

For mapping seabird sensitivity to marine wind farms, we developed a Species Sensitivity Index (SSI) building on frameworks proposed in previous studies (Garthe & Hüppop, 2004; Furness et al., 2013; Bradbury et al., 2014; Certain et al., 2015; Serratos & Allinson, 2022). We then applied the SSI to density-distribution maps of seabird species, whose occurrence along the Portuguese coast overlap with the sites proposed for the implementation of new offshore wind farms. We analyzed 34 seabird species for which distribution maps along the Portuguese coast were available from the Atlas of Marine Birds of Portugal (Meirinho et al., 2014).

We reviewed the literature for each species to mine and compile data on 11 species-specific ecological and behavioural factors related with seabird species' (i) vulnerability to colliding with wind farm structures (4 factors), (ii) vulnerability to displacement due to disturbance by wind farms and associated maintenance (3 factors), and (iii) conservation status (4 factors). In many cases, empirical data to score these is unavailable and existing sensitivity mapping exercises (e.g., Bradbury et al., 2014; Certain et al., 2015; Wade et al., 2016; Serratos & Allinson, 2022) have relied on the scores used in pioneering studies (Garthe & Hüppop, 2004). However, these studies have used data from species and populations from Northern Europe and, for many factors, have used expert knowledge to compensate for the lack of empirical data, which are necessarily qualitative (and thus difficult to reproduce) and tend to be over-conservative. Therefore, whenever possible, we updated data for species (see Methods), particularly for those factors that have been studied in greater detail in recent years using tracking technologies (Bernard et al., 2021; Clairbaux & Jessopp, 2021). The final dataset compiled and used in the analysis is available in Guilherme et al. (2023). Still, knowledge gaps persist and should be tackled in future studies. For example, we could not find any tracking studies for the Mediterranean gull and had to use values from the Black-headed gull (the taxonomically closest species in our dataset) for some of the factors (see Methods).

Using these species-specific factors we first calculated the Collision Vulnerability (CV) and the Displacement Vulnerability (DV) scores of each species. These scores were then weighted by the Conservation Score (CS) to obtain a Collision Sensitivity Index (CSI) and a Displacement Sensitivity Index (DSI) for each species. The final SSI values of each species were the maximum value between the CSI and the DSI after these were rescaled (i.e., to range between 0-1, in order to make them comparable) (see Methods). The 34 seabird species analysed varied considerably in their SSI values ($mean_{SSI} = 0.457$, range: 0.076 – 1.0) (Figure 2; Table 1). We found 19 species to be more sensitive to collision (i.e., $CSI > DSI$), and thus more at risk of direct mortality, while the remaining 15 species were more vulnerable to displacement due to disturbance associated with wind farms (i.e., $CSI < DSI$). The Common scoter, Great black-backed gull, Razorbill, and Audouin's gull stood out in terms of their vulnerability to collision or displacement (i.e., very high CV or DV). However, when vulnerability was weighted by the Conservation Score (CS) of each species, the Balearic Shearwater, Audouin's Gull, and the Common scoter were estimated to be the species with highest sensitivity to marine wind farms (i.e., highest SSI). At the other end, the species with lowest SSI (and thus less sensitive to marine wind farms) were the Arctic tern and the Great skua (Figure 2; Table 1).

Seabird sensitivity to marine wind farms

Figure 2: Seabird species sensitivity to marine wind farms. Closed circles show the vulnerability score (VS), i.e., the highest value between the rescaled (i.e., range 0-1) Collision Vulnerability (CV) and Displacement Vulnerability (DV); silhouettes² show the Species Sensitivity Index (SSI), i.e., the highest value between the rescaled Collision Sensitivity Index (CSI) and Displacement Sensitivity Index (DSI). The 34 seabird species are scored into five categories of sensitivity (very low to very high), according to their VS (closed circles) or their SSI (silhouettes). Species names with an asterisk (*) have CSI > DSI. Species with regular breeding populations along the Portuguese mainland coast are in bold. Number of species per taxonomic group in brackets. Details of seabird species and estimated parameters in Table 1.

Seabird sensitivity to marine wind farms differs spatially throughout the year. The patterns found when the Collision Sensitivity Index (CSI) and the Displacement Sensitivity Index (DSI) were mapped separately were very similar (see Annex I). The final map of Species Sensitivity Index (SSI) shows that the most sensitive areas (i.e., higher SSI) are located along coastal waters, while the areas further offshore (i.e., up to 65 km) are of generally lower sensitivity to seabirds (Figure 3). The areas along the northern and central Portuguese coast (from Caminha to Cascais) are particularly sensitive areas for seabirds, as well as the southern coast (along the Algarve). The south-western coast (along Alentejo) is slightly less sensitive (Figure 3). Accordingly, the overlap between the sites proposed in the PAER and highly sensitive areas for seabirds is noticeably greater in the northern and central coastal areas (Figure 3).

² **Silhouettes from PhyloPic** (<https://www.phylopic.org/>): Ducks – Gabriela Palomo-Munoz; Storm-petrels and Gannets– T. Michael Keesey; Shearwaters – Niamh Esmonde; Cormorants – Ferran Sayol; Phalaropes - Edwin Price; Gulls - Sharon Wegner-Larsen; Terns - Maggie J Watson; Skuas and Auks – Air Kebir NRG.

Table 1: Seabird Species Sensitivity Index (SSI). Collision Vulnerability (CV) and Displacement Vulnerability (DV) were calculated for each species, based on species-specific ecological and behavioural factors (see Methods; Guilherme et al., 2023). CV and DV were weighted by the Conservation Score (CS) to obtain a Collision Sensitivity Index (CSI) and a Displacement Sensitivity Index (DSI) for each species. The final Species Sensitivity Index (SSI) were the highest value between the CSI and the DSI of each species after these were rescaled (i.e., 0-1) (see Methods). The 34 seabird species are classified into five categories of sensitivity (very low to very high). Species with regular breeding populations along the Portuguese mainland coast are in bold. Phenology follows Meirinho et al. (2014): resident (Res), breeder (Breed), migrant (Mig), non-breeder (NBreed).

Group	Species name	Phenology	CV	DV	CS	CSI	DSI	SSI	Sensitivity
Gulls	Audouin's gull (<i>Larus audouinii</i>)	Breed / Mig / NBreed	0.56	0.77	0.83	0.47	0.64	1.0	Very high
Shearwaters	Balearic shearwater (<i>Puffinus mauretanicus</i>)	NBreed (sum, win) / Mig	0.32	0.73	1.00	0.32	0.73	1.0	Very high
Ducks	Common scoter (<i>Melanitta nigra</i>)	NBreed / Mig	0.35	0.97	0.71	0.25	0.69	0.910	Very high
Terns	Common tern (<i>Sterna hirundo</i>)	Mig / Breed	0.52	0.66	0.72	0.37	0.47	0.729	High
Gulls	Great black-backed gull (<i>Larus marinus</i>)	NBreed	0.63	0.58	0.55	0.35	0.32	0.666	High
Auks	Atlantic puffin (<i>Fratercula arctica</i>)	NBreed / Mig	0.23	0.69	0.80	0.19	0.56	0.633	High
Gulls	Black-legged kittiwake (<i>Rissa tridactyla</i>)	NBreed	0.27	0.73	0.75	0.20	0.55	0.618	High
Terns	Sandwich tern (<i>Thalasseus sandvicensis</i>)	NBreed / Mig	0.52	0.79	0.62	0.32	0.49	0.591	Moderate
Cormorants	European shag (<i>Gulosus aristotelis</i>)	Res / NBreed	0.49	0.77	0.66	0.32	0.50	0.585	Moderate
Auks	Razorbill (<i>Alca torda</i>)	NBreed / Mig	0.20	0.90	0.57	0.11	0.51	0.541	Moderate
Auks	Common murre (<i>Uria aalge</i>)	NBreed	0.26	0.79	0.63	0.17	0.50	0.511	Moderate
Gulls	Lesser black-backed gull (<i>Larus fuscus</i>)	Breed / Mig / NBreed	0.37	0.74	0.67	0.25	0.49	0.499	Moderate
Terns	Little tern (<i>Sternula albifrons</i>)	Breed / Mig	0.27	0.74	0.66	0.18	0.49	0.489	Moderate
Skuas	Arctic jaeger (<i>Stercorarius parasiticus</i>)	NBreed / Mig	0.37	0.54	0.78	0.29	0.42	0.483	Moderate
Gannets	Northern gannet (<i>Morus bassanus</i>)	NBreed / Mig	0.44	0.85	0.56	0.24	0.48	0.465	Moderate
Shearwaters	Sooty shearwater (<i>Ardenna grisea</i>)	Mig	0.38	0.48	0.73	0.28	0.35	0.463	Moderate
Phalaropes	Red phalarope (<i>Phalaropus fulicarius</i>)	NBreed / Mig	0.25	0.82	0.55	0.14	0.46	0.418	Moderate
Storm-petrels	Band-rumped storm-petrel (<i>Hydrobates castro</i>)	Breed (win)	0.40	0.54	0.65	0.26	0.35	0.416	Moderate
Gulls	Little gull (<i>Hydrocoloeus minutus</i>)	NBreed / Mig	0.41	0.84	0.54	0.22	0.45	0.412	Moderate
Cormorants	Great cormorant (<i>Phalacrocorax carbo</i>)	Res / NBreed	0.40	0.79	0.56	0.22	0.44	0.387	Low
Gulls	Yellow-legged gull (<i>Larus michahellis</i>)	Res	0.45	0.74	0.53	0.24	0.39	0.349	Low
Shearwaters	Bulwer's petrel (<i>Bulweria bulwerii</i>)	Mig	0.44	0.48	0.54	0.23	0.26	0.335	Low
Shearwaters	Manx shearwater (<i>Puffinus puffinus</i>)	Mig	0.28	0.74	0.56	0.16	0.42	0.334	Low
Gulls	Sabine's gull (<i>Xema sabini</i>)	Mig	0.41	0.70	0.56	0.23	0.40	0.328	Low
Storm-petrels	Wilson's storm-petrel (<i>Oceanites oceanicus</i>)	Mig	0.40	0.48	0.57	0.23	0.27	0.319	Low
Gulls	Mediterranean gull (<i>Larus melanocephalus</i>)	NBreed / Mig	0.41	0.60	0.55	0.23	0.33	0.313	Low
Shearwaters	Great shearwater (<i>Ardenna gravis</i>)	Mig	0.38	0.48	0.57	0.22	0.27	0.290	Low
Shearwaters	Cory's shearwater (<i>Calonectris borealis</i>)	Breed	0.31	0.54	0.68	0.21	0.37	0.271	Low
Skuas	Pomarine jaeger (<i>Stercorarius pomarinus</i>)	Mig	0.37	0.63	0.56	0.21	0.35	0.260	Low
Gulls	Black-headed gull (<i>Larus ridibundus</i>)	Mig / NBreed / Breed	0.27	0.67	0.55	0.15	0.37	0.240	Low
Terns	Black tern (<i>Chlidonias niger</i>)	Mig	0.27	0.67	0.55	0.15	0.37	0.236	Low
Storm-petrels	European storm-petrel (<i>Hydrobates pelagicus</i>)	Mig	0.35	0.48	0.55	0.19	0.26	0.212	Low
Terns	Arctic tern (<i>Sterna paradisaea</i>)	Mig	0.32	0.52	0.56	0.18	0.29	0.176	Very low
Skuas	Great skua (<i>Catharacta skua</i>)	NBreed / Mig	0.25	0.48	0.57	0.14	0.28	0.076	Very low

Seabird Sensitivity to marine wind farms

Figure 3: Seabird sensitivity to marine wind farm expansion in Portugal.

Seabird sensitivity to marine wind farm expansion in Portugal was calculated using density-distribution maps (ind.s per 4x4 km grid cells) across the seasons of the year each species occurs in Portugal (Meirinho et al., 2014), and a Species Sensitivity Index (SSI) estimated using species-specific factors related with species' vulnerability to collision with, and displacement due disturbance from, marine wind farms. For each of the 34 species, we multiplied the natural log of the density in each grid cell by the respective SSI value (Table 1). The final map was obtained by summing the values in each cell across species (see Methods). Isolines delineate five categories of sensitivity: low (dark blue) to very high (dark red). Boundaries of proposed wind farm sites are in white (the Aguçadoura site is a pilot marine wind farm in operation since 2020).

Standing out as particularly worrying sites are:

- The two sites of Viana do Castelo (North and South), as (i) they overlap with areas of high sensitivity for seabirds, (ii) their proximity to the coast leads the migratory corridor to gradually taper off into a narrow corridor between (future) wind farms and the coast, (iii) they are in the vicinity of an area adjacent to the border located in Spain's waters (cumulating the impacts of these structures on migratory birds, the effects of which remain unknown).
- The Ericeira site, as it (i) overlaps with the areas of high sensitivity and (ii) is located between two SPAs (Ilhas Berlengas and Cabo Raso; see Figure 1), imposing a barrier to seabirds on the move, particularly during migrations, when these areas are particularly important for species such as the Northern gannet and the Balearic shearwater (Cabo Raso Standard Data Form³). Moreover, this area is in the vicinity (~35 km) of the only mainland breeding colonies of Cory's shearwater and Band-rumped storm-petrel (Ilhas Berlengas Standard Data Form⁴); so the presence of wind farms can negatively affect these species during their foraging trips during the breeding season (e.g., Peschko et al., 2020). Indeed, tracking data has

³ Cabo Raso SPA PTZPE0061 Standard Data Form: <https://natura2000.eea.europa.eu/Natura2000/SDF.aspx?site=PTZPE0061>

⁴ Ilhas Berlengas SPA PTZPE0009 Standard Data Form: <https://natura2000.eea.europa.eu/natura2000/SDF.aspx?site=PTZPE0009>

confirmed the existence of foraging grounds used by Cory's shearwaters breeding in Berlengas within the proposed Ericeira site (Haug et al., 2015).

It is important to highlight that our approach may probably have underestimated the sensitivity within and around the Sines site – particularly for migratory seabirds (Figure 3). The methodology used to produce the base maps for the Atlas of Seabirds of Portugal (i.e., observations at sea on boat transects; Meirinho et al., 2014) does not capture migratory peaks of migratory species, nor the exact routes taken by the birds actively migrating. Recent tracking studies suggest that, along the Portuguese mainland coast, actively migrating seabirds tend to use areas closer to the coast along the northern part of the coast, but take a direct, more offshore path between the Cape Espichel and the Cape of São Vicente, potentially crossing the Sines site; this is the case for important species, such as the Balearic Shearwater (PNA Puffin Baléares⁵; Wikelski et al., 2023) and the Northern Gannet (Gannet juvenile GPS-PTT data Bass Rock 2018-19⁶; BirdLife International, 2023).

2. Areas of importance for other marine biodiversity

We focused on the sensitivity of seabirds because they are particularly vulnerable to energy infrastructure and are the taxa more at risk from marine wind farms (Garthe & Hüppop, 2004). Nevertheless, these structures may also affect other biodiversity, including shorebirds and marine mammals (Madsen et al., 2006; Lloret et al., 2022; Schwemmer et al., 2023). However, knowledge on the distributions and ecology of these species groups remains limited, which precluded mapping their sensitivity in the same way we have done for seabirds. Nevertheless, we decided to analyse the potential areas more problematic for shorebirds and marine mammals, even if using a more simplistic approach, to emphasise the importance of considering the potential effects of marine wind farms on these species, and the need to invest in their research.

2.1. Areas at sea important for shorebirds

We mapped areas at sea potentially sensitive for shorebirds when approaching or departing coastal wetlands. We created a radius around each of 13 wetlands considered *important* and *very important* for shorebirds (5 and 20 km respectively) (see Methods).

Areas at sea important for shorebirds are located along all the Portuguese coast, being of particular importance those located off the main estuaries (i.e., Tejo and Sado) and 'Rias' (i.e., Aviero and Formosa) (Figure 4). None of these areas overlap the proposed sites for marine wind farm construction. Nevertheless, it should be stressed the exact routes and flight heights shorebirds use during their coastal movements – particularly during migration – are still poorly understood, so the potential impacts of the proposed sites for wind farm construction remain largely unknown.

5 Project PNA Puffin Baléares (ID 2266929053) in Movebank (2023): https://www.movebank.org/cms/webapp?gwt_fragment=page=studies,path=study2266929053 [Accessed 01/10/2023]

6 Project Gannet juvenile GPS-PTT data Bass Rock 2018-19 (ID 1815) in Seabird Tracking Database (BirdLife International 2023): <https://data.seabirdtracking.org/dataset/1815> [Accessed 01/10/2023]

Areas at sea important for shorebirds

Figure 4: Areas at sea important for shorebirds.

Areas at sea potentially sensitive for shorebirds when approaching or departing coastal wetlands, according to wetland importance for shorebirds (see Methods). Note that shorebird migratory routes were not included in this analysis as this information remains unknown. Boundaries of proposed wind farm sites are in white.

2.2. Areas of importance for marine mammals

We mapped marine mammal species richness and species density to visualise areas of importance (and thus potentially sensitive) for these species. For mapping marine mammal species richness (cetacean species per 8×8 km grid cell) we compiled 8097 observations from 13 cetacean species from different sources (SPEA, *unpublished data*; iNaturalist, 2023; Correia et al., 2019; Grilo et al., 2022) (see Methods). As the use of observation-only data can strongly bias observed patterns, we mapped marine mammal density (cetacean observations per 8×8 km grid cell) using observations 1753 observations from 9 species obtained in systematic vessel-based surveys covering all the Portuguese coast (SPEA, *unpublished data*) (see Methods).

Marine mammals occur along the whole Portuguese mainland coast, with the highest number of species for which there were observations found along the Algarve southern coast (Figure 5a). However, these patterns of importance differ when the density of species is taken into account. The species density map reveals a more homogeneous distribution of importance along the entire Portuguese coast, with areas of greater importance (i.e., greater density of cetaceans) located along the northern and central coasts, as well as along the Algarve coast (Figure 5b). The areas of highest importance (both in terms of richness and density) do not fall within any of the

proposed sites for wind farm construction; however, similarly to shorebirds, these results should be taken as preliminary and interpreted with caution because the annual distributions of marine mammals along the Portuguese coast remain poorly studied.

Figure 5: Areas of importance for marine mammals. (a) Marine mammal species richness (i.e., number of species with records per 8×8 km grid cells), based on 8097 observations from 13 species of cetaceans (see Methods); and (b) Marine mammal species density (i.e., number of species records per 8×8 km grid cells), based on 1753 observations from 9 species of cetaceans obtained from systematic vessel-based surveys (see Methods). These results should be taken as preliminary and interpreted with caution because the annual distributions of cetaceans along the Portuguese coast are still poorly known. Boundaries of proposed wind farm sites are in white.

3. Risk at the sites proposed for marine wind farm construction

When looking at each proposed site individually, all sites but Figueira da Foz are used by more seabirds than the average in the entire study area (according to the mean density of species in each site *vs* in the study area) (Figure 6). As expected, Viana do Castelo North, Viana do Castelo South, and Ericeira (i.e., the three sites with higher SSI) were also the sites with higher mean density of birds throughout the year (Figure 6). Moreover, these three sites were the ones hosting a higher number of species, as well as higher numbers of high and very high sensitive species (Table 2). Regarding marine mammals, all sites had relatively low number of species, as the southern coast along the Algarve had the highest number of recorded species (Table 2; Figure 5a).

Figure 6: Mean density of seabird species in each proposed site. Barplot to the left shows the mean density of seabird species occurring in each of the sites proposed for wind farm construction (excluding grid cells with density < 0.1); vertical bar shows the mean density across the entire study area (see Methods). The map to the right shows the seabird SSI within each proposed site (same data as shown in Figure 3).

Table 2: Species richness in each proposed site. For each site the number of marine mammal species, seabird species, breeding seabird species, and sensitive species (i.e., with very high and high sensitivity; Table 1) is given.

Proposed site	No. seabird species	No. breeding seabird species	No. sensitive seabird species	No. Marine mammals
Viana do Castelo Norte	19	5	5	3
Viana do Castelo Sul	20	6	5	3
Leixões	16	4	4	3
Figueira da Foz	14	3	4	3
Ericeira	19	5	5	1
Sines	15	4	4	2

The importance of the three proposed sites of greatest concern – i.e., Viana do Castelo Norte, Viana do Castelo Sul, and Ericeira – for some species is evident (Figure 7). These three sites overlap with areas particularly important for the Manx shearwater, Yellow-legged gull, Northern gannet, Lesser black-backed gull, Black-legged kittiwake, and the Atlantic puffin, as the mean density of these species within the limits of the three sites is higher than the mean density observed across the entire study area. In addition, the Viana do Castelo Sul site overlaps an area particularly important for the Common murre. The Ericeira site is in a particularly important area for Cory's shearwaters (Figure 7), due to its proximity to the breeding colony in the Berlengas Islands.

Figure 7: Mean seabird species density in the three proposed sites of greatest concern. Bars show the mean density of each species in the proposed sites of Viana do Castelo Norte, Viana do Castelo Sul, and Ericeira, which overlap with areas of high sensitivity for seabirds (Figure 3). Grid cells with density < 0.1 were excluded (see Methods). Horizontal dark lines show the mean density of each species across the entire study area. Seabird species are ordered by increasing sensitivity (i.e., SSI; Table 1).

CONCLUSIONS

This is the first study to identify the areas of greatest sensitivity of seabirds to offshore wind farm expansion in Portugal. Our results provide a benchmark for future analysis and a valuable contribution to inform ongoing policy decision making, as well as for helping establish robust guidelines for environmental impact assessment for new marine wind farm projects.

Integrating new information into the decision-making process

Finding the best solutions to reconcile the profitability of marine wind farms, other human uses (e.g., fisheries), and biodiversity conservation is a complex process (e.g., Best & Halpin, 2019) in which all the key stakeholders must be involved from the outset (Brignon et al., 2022; Virtanen et al., 2022). Inevitably, this is a process in which all stakeholders have to make concessions, so the decision-making process must be based on the best existing information. Although the involvement of all key stakeholders was not a reality from the start of the process (namely nature conservation NGOs; Parecer SPEA⁷), the results presented here call for the need to re-evaluate the sites proposed in the PAER (DGRM, 2023a). The sites of Viana do Castelo North, Viana do Castelo South, and Ericeira stand out because they overlap with areas of high sensitivity for seabirds. Furthermore, the Ericeira site overlaps an area used by Cory's shearwaters during the breeding season, and is positioned between two SPAs, creating a potential barrier to the movement of birds between these areas (particularly during migration periods).

Integrating knowledge across scales

We restricted our analyses to waters up to 65 km offshore to reflect the sites proposed in the PAER and, therefore, our results must be interpreted in light of the scale of analysis. If we had analysed a larger area such as the entire Exclusive Economic Zone (EEZ), the sensitivity map would be different as the entire study area (i.e., up to 65 km) would likely appear as highly sensitive. Likewise, the sensitivity maps do not necessarily reflect the site-scale sensitivity patterns in each proposed site. Therefore, site-specific studies are needed to understand the long-term effects of these structures in marine biodiversity, and design corresponding minimization action. In line with other European countries, we recommend that all sites be subject to rigorous monitoring, including before and after studies involving control and impacted areas (BACI methodology; e.g., Degraer & Brabant, 2009; Garthe et al., 2023).

Assessing cumulative impacts along the migratory flyway

Although the effects of a single marine wind farm may be relatively small on the population of a given seabird species, the cumulative effect of several marine wind farms along its distribution range could amplify these effects with harmful consequences at the population level (Busch & Garthe, 2018; Goodale et al., 2019). However, the consequences of cumulative effects of several wind farms on seabirds – and shorebirds – remain largely unknown, notably for migratory species that are particularly difficult to study when they are far from their breeding colonies. Portugal hosts abundant numbers of seabirds during migratory periods, so the effects of new wind farms could be harmful to their populations. As the strategy for the development of offshore wind farms is a European endeavour

⁷ Parecer SPEA: <https://spea.pt/campanhas/parecer-spea-a-proposta-preliminar-para-localizacao-das-areas-de-implantacao-das-eolicas-offshore-na-costa-continental-portuguesa/>

(European Commission, 2021), so should be the understanding of the cumulative impacts these structures may have on our shared natural heritage. Therefore, we recommend that the sensitivity mapping exercise herein presented should be complemented with species-specific studies conducted in partnership with the countries where these species breed. On the other hand, a cumulative effect can also occur with other threats to these species (Dias et al., 2019). Many of the seabird species that use the Portuguese mainland EEZ – including some of the most sensitive to offshore wind farms – are affected by other human activities such as bycatch in fishing boats (Oliveira et al., 2015), diseases such as the avian flu (Cunningham et al., 2022), or predation by invasive species at their colonies (e.g., Rodríguez et al., 2019). All the additional causes of population declines already occurring should be considered when evaluating the impact of wind farm development on seabirds and other marine biodiversity.

METHODS

1. Seabird sensitivity to marine wind farms

For mapping seabird sensitivity to marine wind farms, we used seabird species-density distribution maps and applied a Species Sensitivity Index (SSI), building on frameworks developed in previous studies (Garthe & Hüppop, 2004; Furness et al., 2013; Bradbury et al., 2014; Certain et al., 2015; Serratos & Allinson, 2022).

We analyzed all seabird species that occur regularly in the Portuguese EEZ adjacent to the mainland coast up to ($n = 34$), for which distribution maps are available from the Atlas of Marine Birds of Portugal⁸ (Meirinho et al., 2014). These included species from several species groups: ducks (Anatidae; $n = 1$ species), storm-petrels (Hydrobatidae and Oceanitidae; 3 species), shearwaters (Procellariidae; 6 species), gannets (Sulidae; 1 species), cormorants (Phalacrocoracidae, 2 species), phalaropes (Scolopacidae, 1 species), gulls and terns (Lariidae; 14 species), skuas (Stercorariidae; 3 species), and auks (Alcidae; 3 species) (Table 1).

1.1. Species-density distribution maps

The distribution maps available in the Atlas of Marine Birds of Portugal (Meirinho et al., 2014) show the probability of occurrence (percentage per 4×4 km grid cell; raster format) of each species in each season of the year (i.e., spring, summer, autumn, and winter), modeled from species presence data obtained from systematic vessel-based marine surveys (using the European Seabirds At Sea (ESAS) methodology; Stone et al., 1995). More details regarding the habitat models used to map the probability of occurrence can be found in Meirinho et al. (2014). All species-season maps were clipped with a 65 km buffer from the Portuguese mainland coast, corresponding to the maximum distance of the proposed sites for wind farm concessions from the coast (DGRM, 2023b).

We then estimated the density of birds (individuals per 4×4 km grid cell) for each species-season map, using (i) an estimate of the population size of each species in Portuguese waters, and (ii) the relative importance of each season for each species. First, we calculated the population size of each species by multiplying the estimated proportion of the regional (i.e., European) population occurring in Portugal (mean values obtained in the Red Data Book of the Vertebrates of Portugal; Cabral et al., 2005) by the species' European population size (obtained in the European Red List of Birds; BirdLife International, 2021). For species with no estimates available, we considered 0.1% of the European population (e.g., Black tern), or 0.01% of the global population (e.g., Great shearwater; BirdLife International, 2023). Second, we estimated the relative importance (%) of each season for each species, relatively to the number of seasons the species was present along the Portuguese coast (i.e., a species-season distribution map was available) using ESAS observation data (mean abundance for the 2004 – 2023 period; SPEA, *unpublished data*). This approach attributed more weight to species that used the Portuguese waters for longer throughout the year, such that the sum of the importance of a species that occurred in all four seasons equaled 1, the sum of the importance of a species that occurred in three seasons equaled 0.75, 0.5 for species that occurred in two seasons, and 0.25 for species present in one season. Finally, we estimated the density of birds for each species-season map:

$$\text{Season density} = (\text{Population} \times \text{Season importance}) \times (\text{Prob. occurrence} / \sum \text{Prob. occurrence})$$

8 **Atlas of Marine Birds of Portugal:** <https://www.atlasavesmarinhas.pt/>

For seven species that regularly breed in Portugal (Table 1) we generated maps of projected distributions during the breeding season (individuals per 4×4 km grid cell), using an adaptation of the foraging radius approach (Soanes et al., 2016), which is based on data on colony location and number of breeding pairs (following Critchley et al., 2018). Projected distributions assumed that the birds forage within a certain distance around the colony (corresponding to the maximum foraging range known for the species during the breeding season), and that the use of the areas decay with the distance from the colony (Critchley et al., 2018). Foraging ranges were lifted from published tracking studies (carried out in Portugal, when available). For Cory's shearwater and Band-rumped storm-petrel, which perform short and long foraging trips, we used the maximum foraging distance during short-trips (Figure 8). These projected distributions were merged to the corresponding species-season maps produced above: first we summed the above-mentioned spring and summer species density maps, and then merged the projected distribution to this selecting the maximum value between corresponding cells. For the Band-rumped storm-petrel we used the maps for autumn and winter as the species breeds during those months (Grandeiro et al., 1998).

Projected seabird density around colonies

Figure 8: Projected seabird distribution around breeding colonies.

Map shows the projected density (individuals per 4×4 km grid cell) around the breeding colonies of seven seabird species that regularly breed in Portugal: Band-rumped storm-petrel, Cory's shearwater, European shag, Audouin's gull, Yellow-legged gull, Lesser black-backed gull, and Little tern.

Finally, we merged all species-season-density maps to get a **final year-round species-density distribution map** for each of the 34 seabird species, by summing the estimated values across overlapping cells (Figure 9).

Figure 9: Year-round species-density distribution maps produced for the 34 seabird species analyzed. Maps show the estimated density (individuals per 4×4 km grid cell) of each species along the Portuguese coastal waters (details on species in Table 1).

1.2. Seabird Species Sensitivity Index (SSI)

For each species, we calculated a Species Sensitivity Index (SSI), as the maximum rescaled value (see below) between the species' Collision Sensitivity Index (CSI) and Displacement Sensitivity Index (DSI), similar to the approach used by Bradbury et al. (2014).

We used the equations proposed by Certain et al. (2015) to calculate the CSI and the DSI for each species:

$$\text{Collision Sensitivity Index (CSI)} = \text{Collision Vulnerability} \times \text{Conservation Score}$$

$$\text{Displacement Sensitivity Index (DSI)} = \text{Displacement Vulnerability} \times \text{Conservation Score}$$

$$\text{Species Sensitivity Index (SSI)} = \text{Sensitivity Index}_{\max(\text{Collision}, \text{Displacement})}$$

Below, we detail the calculation of each species' Collision Vulnerability (CV), Displacement Vulnerability (DV), and Conservation Score (CS), based on species-specific ecological and behavioural factors related with species' (i) vulnerability to colliding with wind farm structures, (ii) vulnerability to being disturbed and/or displaced by wind farms and associated maintenance, and (iii) conservation status and ability to recover from wind farm impacts. The final dataset of factors compiled and used in the analysis is available in Guilherme et al. (2023).

1.2.1. Collision Vulnerability (CV)

Seabirds that are at greatest risk of colliding with wind farms are those that spend more time flying at collision risk height with turbine blades, spend more time flying at sea, have high nocturnal flight activity, and those that have poor flight manoeuvrability to avoid wind farm structures (Garthe & Hüppop, 2004).

To estimate Collision Vulnerability (CV), *time flying at collision risk height (CV.1)* and *time flying at sea (CV.2)* were considered primary factors. As the amount of time a given bird spends flying at collision risk height is dependent on the amount of time it spends flying at sea (i.e., CV.2 is conditional on CV.1), we used a multiplicative relationship between these two factors (Certain et al., 2015). *Nocturnal flight activity (CV.3)* and *flight manoeuvrability (CV.4)* were considered aggravating factors (Certain et al., 2015):

$$\text{Collision Vulnerability} = (CV.1 \times CV.2)^{\left(\frac{1 - CV.3 + CV.4}{2}\right) / \left(\frac{CV.3 + CV.4}{2} + 0.5\right)}$$

Where,

Time flying at collision risk height (CV.1): The amount of time a bird spends flying at sea at turbine blade height is one of the main factors influencing collision risk of seabirds (Cook et al., 2012; Furness et al., 2013; Johnston et al., 2014; Bradbury et al., 2014). We compiled information from the literature regarding the percentage of time flying at collision risk height (*ca.* 20 -150 m *a.s.l.*; Furness et al., 2013) for each of the species considered. This was represented either as percentage of birds observed at collision risk height (e.g., Paton et al., 2010; Cook et al., 2012), or as percentage of time spent at collision risk height modeled from tracking data (e.g., Courbin et al., 2023). Previous studies have proposed expressing flight time at risk of collision in percentage (Furness et al., 2013; Bradbury et al., 2014); however, we found that SSI values are highly sensitive to small differences in the percentages considered, resulting in very different SSI estimates between similar species (e.g., Great shearwater and Sooty shearwater). Therefore, we ranked time flying at collision risk into five categories (following Garthe & Hüppop, 2004): 1 ($\leq 5\%$ of time flying at collision risk), 2 (5-10%), 3 (10–15%), 4 (15–20%), and 5 ($>25\%$). These scores were then divided by 5 to be comprised between 0.2 and 1 (following Certain et al., 2015).

Available studies considered slightly different heights when assessing collision risk height (*mean minimum height* = 22.7 m, range 20-50 m; *mean maximum height* = 155.8, range 120-350 m). Whenever height values were available from multiple studies (either from observations or tracking), for a given species, we used the mean value across studies. We found flight height information for 28 species (82%) in our dataset. For the remaining species ($n = 6$), we used percentage values from the taxonomically closest species in our dataset, or the median value across closest relatives.

Time flying at sea (CV.2): The higher the time a bird spends flying at sea, the higher is the risk of colliding with wind farms (Furness et al., 2013). We reviewed tracking data studies on seabird activity patterns to collect the percentage of time spent flying for all species in our dataset, building from recent reviews of existing seabird tracking data (Bernard et al., 2021; Clairbaux & Jessopp, 2021). Whenever available, we extracted data referring

to flight activity during the day and to the most important period of the year (e.g., breeding, non-breeding) for each of the species in Portuguese waters. We could find data from tracking studies reporting the percentage of time flying for 21 species (62%). For the remaining species ($n = 13$), we used score values reported in previous studies (e.g., Garthe & Hüppop, 2004; Bradbury et al., 2014). We found a strong correlation between the percentage of time spent flying based on data collected from tracking studies and the scores collected from previous studies (Spearman's rank correlation, $\rho = 0.711$, $n = 19$). This supported our decision of using values based on the scores from previous studies for the species for which we could not find any tracking studies. We standardize all values compiled into five categories (Garthe & Hüppop, 2004): 1 (0–20% of time at sea was spent in flight), 2 (21–40%), 3 (41–60%), 4 (61–80%), and 5 (81–100%). Scores were then divided by 5, to make them between 0.2 and 1 (Certain et al., 2015).

Nocturnal flight activity (CV.3): Nocturnal flying can exacerbate the risk of collision with wind turbines due to reduced obstacle detectability in low light conditions (Travers, 2023). Existing nocturnal flight data is very limited and unavailable for most species (Furness et al., 2013), and previous studies have relied on expert opinion to score seabird nocturnal flight activity (Garthe & Hüppop, 2004; Furness et al., 2013). We attempted to extract percentage data from tracking studies on flight activity (see above *Proportion of time flying at sea*); however, for most species ($n = 25$) it was not possible to separate between day and night flight and we used qualitative scores from previous studies (Willmot et al., 2013; Bradbury et al., 2014). As for time flying at sea, we ranked all values into five categories (Garthe & Hüppop, 2004): 1 (low nocturnal flight activity), to 5 (high nocturnal flight activity). Scores were then divided by 5 (i.e., 0.2 – 1; Certain et al., 2015).

Flight manoeuvrability (CV.4): Flight manoeuvrability denotes the ability of a bird changing the speed and direction of flight, such that species with low flight manoeuvrability are expected to be less capable of avoiding obstacles and are, thus, potentially more vulnerable to strikes with wind farms (Gauld et al., 2022). Flight manoeuvrability can be calculated as the ratio between a bird's body mass and its wing loading (i.e., area of the wings; Rogalla et al., 2021). However, as data on wing loadings is scarce and unavailable for most bird species, we used data on wing length and wing width (from the AVONET database; Tobias et al., 2022) as proxies for wing loading, and calculated flight manoeuvrability (following Reid et al., 2023):

$$\text{flight manoeuvrability} = \text{body mass} / (\text{wing length} \times \text{wing width})$$

The flight manoeuvrability values were ranked into five categories (following Reid et al., 2023): 1 (< 0.01), 2 (0.01-0.02), 3 (0.02-0.03), 4 (0.03-0.04), and 5 (>0.04). These scores were then divided by 5 (i.e., 0.2 – 1; Certain et al., 2015). A Spearman's rank correlation contrasting the flight manoeuvrability values calculated using wing length and wing width, with flight manoeuvrability values calculated using wing loading for 25 species in our dataset (data from Rogalla et al., 2021), indicated this was a robust approach ($\rho = 0.947$, $n = 30$ species).

1.2.2. Displacement Vulnerability (DV)

Some seabirds actively avoid offshore wind farms, which may lead to displacement from areas with wind farms. Seabirds may be vulnerable to displacement due to disturbance by wind farm structures, and/or due to

disturbance by vessels and helicopters (during construction phase and maintenance operations). The ability for these species to explore alternative habitats – i.e., their habitat flexibility –, or lack thereof, may attenuate or accentuate the effects from displacement (see below).

To estimate Displacement Vulnerability (DV), **disturbance by wind farm structures (DV.1)** and **disturbance by vessels and helicopters (DV.2)** were considered primary factors with an additive relationship. **Habitat flexibility (DV.3)** was considered an aggravating factor (Certain et al., 2015):

$$\text{Disturbance Vulnerability} = \left(\frac{DV.1 + DV.2}{2} \right)^{\left(\frac{1 - DV.3}{DV.3 + 0.5} \right)}$$

Where,

Disturbance by wind farm structures (DV.1): Some seabird species avoid offshore wind farms, which may lead to loss of foraging habitat, and to the need of performing longer flights to different feeding grounds. Other seabirds, on the other hand, are attracted to wind farms, which may result in higher direct mortality by collision. Data on the avoidance behaviour for each species were obtained from a review of seabird avoidance responses from operating wind farms (Dierschke et al., 2016), which we completed with data from other sources (e.g., Wade et al., 2016). We found no data for 10 species and, as above, we considered the values from the closest species in our dataset. We ranked disturbance by wind farm structures into five categories: 1 (low disturbance), to 5 (high disturbance). These scores were then divided by 5 (i.e., 0.2 – 1; Certain et al., 2015).

Disturbance by vessels and helicopters (DV.2): The construction of offshore wind farms and their maintenance require regular traffic of vessels and helicopters to, in, and from the area. This increased marine traffic likely leads to higher disturbance to seabirds and other biodiversity. Data on the escape response produced by vessel and helicopter traffic on seabirds were taken from Fliessbach et al. (2019). For the species ($n = 20$) for which data were not available we used scores from previous studies (e.g., Garthe & Hüppop, 2004; Willmot et al., 2013; Wade et al., 2016). We ranked disturbance by vessels and helicopters into five categories: 1 (low disturbance), to 5 (high disturbance). These scores were then divided by 5 (i.e., 0.2 – 1; Certain et al., 2015).

Habitat flexibility (DV.3): Habitat flexibility refers to the capacity of a species to feed on different sources and/or forage in a variety of habitats (Furness et al., 2013). Therefore, species with low habitat flexibility have lower ability to, and are at more risk from, habitat changes (Cooke et al., 2019), namely those occurring from the construction and maintenance of marine wind farms. To describe habitat flexibility, we used the number ($\text{Log}_{10}+1$) of IUCN habitats listed as *suitable* (following Richards et al., 2020), considering the breeding and non-breeding habitats for species that breed in Portugal, and only non-breeding habitats for those species that do not breed. We ranked the habitat flexibility values into five categories: 1 (high habitat flexibility) to 5 (low habitat flexibility). These scores were then divided by 5 (i.e., 0.2 – 1; Certain et al., 2015).

1.2.3. Conservation Score (CS)

Threat and conservation status are often used as proxies to evaluate a species' ability to respond and recover from ongoing pressures and threats (Garthe & Hüppop, 2004; Akçakaya et al., 2018). We considered three levels of Red List conservation status to score seabirds in our dataset: Portuguese Conservation status (Cabral et al., 2005), European Conservation status (BirdLife International, 2021), and Global Conservation status (BirdLife International, 2023). For each of the three levels, conservation status were ranked into five categories: 1 (Least Concern), 2 (Near threatened), 3 (Vulnerable), 4 (Endangered), and 5 (Critically Endangered) (Reid et al., 2023), divided by 5 (i.e., 0.2 – 1; Certain et al., 2015).

To estimate the Conservation Score (CS), *Portuguese Conservation status (Con.1)*, *European Conservation status (Con.2)*, and *Global Conservation status (Con.3)*, were considered primary factors, whereas *Adult annual survival (Con.4)* was considered an aggravating factor (following Certain et al., 2015):

$$\text{Conservation score (CS)} = \left(\frac{\text{Con.1} + \text{Con.2} + \text{Con.3}}{3} \right)^{(1 - \text{Con.4}) / (\text{Con.4} + 0.5)}$$

Where,

Annual adult survival (Con.4): Mortality is a direct consequence of collision with wind farms, thus species with high annual survival rates (and corresponding low productivity) are potentially more affected than species with low survival rates (Garthe & Hüppop, 2004). We revised and updated ($n = 26$ species; 74%) the annual survival values (i.e., percentage) provided in Bird et al. (2020). Whenever possible, we prioritised studies of populations within or closest to our study area. When several studies were available, for a given species, we used the mean value across studies. For four species, we found no data in which cases we used values from the closest species in our dataset. We used annual adult survival as percentage, expressed as decimal fraction (i.e., 0-1).

1.3. Mapping seabird sensitivity to marine wind farms

For each species, we produced a wind farm sensitivity map, by integrating their respective sensitivity indices to collision (i.e., *CSI*) and to disturbance (i.e., *DSI*), with the species' final density distribution map (see 1.1). The final SSI value used in the equation below was the highest between the CSI and DSI calculated for each species (Furness et al., 2013). However, because CSI and DSI are not quantitatively comparable (as the impacts on populations from disturbance are likely considerably lower than direct mortality due collision; Furness et al., 2013), we rescaled CSI and DSI (i.e., to range between 0-1) in order to make them comparable and selected the highest between the two as the final SSI for each species.

$$\text{Species Wind farm Sensitivity} = \ln(\text{density}_{\text{species}} + 1) \times \text{Sensitivity Index}_{\max(\text{Collision}, \text{Displacement})}$$

Finally, we mapped seabird sensitivity to offshore wind farms by combining the maps produced for all 34 species:

$$\text{Wind farm Sensitivity} = \sum_{\text{species}} \ln(\text{density}_{\text{species}} + 1) \times \text{Sensitivity Index}_{\max(\text{Collision}, \text{Displacement})}$$

2. Areas of importance for other marine biodiversity

2.1. Areas at sea important for shorebirds

We mapped areas at sea potentially sensitive for shorebirds when approaching or departing from coastal wetlands. We scored 13 coastal wetlands recognised by the Agreement on the Conservation of African-Eurasian Migratory Waterbirds (UNEP/CMS, 2018) as of international importance for the conservation of shorebirds (data available in the Critical Site Network tool⁹). Then, we considered a radius around each wetland (20 km for wetlands classified as highly important – i.e., those holding more than 15 000 birds of the species covered by the AEWA – and 5 km for the wetlands considered as important), which represents the areas at sea potentially sensitive for shorebirds when approaching or departing from these areas (Table 3).

Table 3: List of wetlands and respective importance.

Wetland	Importance
Estuário do Minho	Important
Barrinha de Esmoriz	Important
Ria de Aveiro	Highly important
Estuário do Mondego	Important
Estuário do Tejo	Highly important
Lagoa de Albufeira	Important
Estuário do Sado	Highly important
Lagoa de Santo André	Important
Estuário do Mira	Important
Ria do Alvor	Important
Lagoa dos Salgados	Important
Ria Formosa	Highly important
Castro Marim	Important

2.2. Areas of importance for marine mammals

Areas of importance, and thus potentially sensitive, for marine mammals were assessed mapping marine mammal species richness and species density. For building these maps we used observations obtained in systematic vessel-based surveys covering all the Portuguese coast (using ESAS methodology; SPEA, *unpublished data*). For mapping marine mammal species richness we completed these data with observations from other databases publicly available online (iNaturalist, 2023; Correia et al., 2019; Grilo et al., 2022). Only species with a minimum of 5 observations available were considered, resulting in a total of 8097 observations from 13 cetacean species used in the analysis (Table 4). To visualise marine mammal species richness we binned all observations in a 8×8 km cell grid, and summed the number of species found in each grid cell. For mapping marine mammal density (i.e., cetacean observations per 8×8 km grid cell) we only used the ESAS data (SPEA, *unpublished data*), which included 1753 observations from 9 species (only considering species with a minimum of 5 records) (Table 1). To visualise marine mammal density these data were binned in the same grid used for the richness map, summing up all records in each cell.

⁹ **Critical Site Network tool:** <https://criticalsites.wetlands.org/>

Table 4: Marine mammal species. For each species, the number of observations used to produce the richness map and the density map, and the Conservation status in Portugal is shown (Critically Endangered – CR; Vulnerable – VU; Near Threatened – NT; Least Concern – LC; Data Deficient – DD; and Not Evaluated – NEval).

Group	Name	n richness	n density	Conservation status
Balaenopteridae	Minke Whale (<i>Balaenoptera acutorostrata</i>)	184	22	VU
Balaenopteridae	Sei Whale (<i>Balaenoptera borealis</i>)	5	–	NEval
Balaenopteridae	Fin Whale (<i>Balaenoptera physalus</i>)	29	5	VU
Balaenopteridae	Humpback Whale (<i>Megaptera novaeangliae</i>)	10	–	NEval
Delphinidae	Common Dolphin (<i>Delphinus delphis</i>)	5519	1463	NT
Delphinidae	Long-finned Pilot Whale (<i>Globicephala melas</i>)	10	9	DD
Delphinidae	unidentified pilot whale (<i>Globicephala sp.</i>)	10	8	–
Delphinidae	Risso's Dolphin (<i>Grampus griseus</i>)	101	9	VU
Delphinidae	Killer Whale (<i>Orcinus orca</i>)	38	–	CR
Delphinidae	False Killer Whale (<i>Pseudorca crassidens</i>)	6	–	NEval
Delphinidae	Striped Dolphin (<i>Stenella coeruleoalba</i>)	111	16	LC
Delphinidae	Bottlenose Dolphin (<i>Tursiops truncatus</i>)	1757	213	LC
Phocoenidae	Harbour Porpoise (<i>Phocoena phocoena</i>)	312	8	CR
Ziphiidae	unidentified beaked whale (<i>Mesoplodon sp.</i>)	5	–	–

3. Risk at the sites proposed for marine wind farm construction

For each of the six sites proposed for the installation of offshore wind farms we calculated the (i) mean seabird species density, (ii) species richness (seabirds and cetaceans), (iii) number of sensitive seabird species (i.e., with moderate, high, and very high sensitivity), and (iv) number of breeding seabird species (considering all grid cells with density > 0.1, within or partially within the limits of each proposed site). To better understand the risk for each species we compared the species density within each of the proposed sites of highest concern with the species density across the entire study area.

3.1. Proposed sites and marine biodiversity conservation instruments

To map potential conflicts (e.g., overlap, juxtaposition, adjacency) of the proposed areas for the construction of new wind farms with areas of importance for marine biodiversity, we mapped the boundaries of the main natural resource and marine biodiversity management instruments along the Portuguese coast, including Protected Areas (PA), Special Protection Areas (SPA), Sites of Community Importance (SCI), as well as globally Important Bird & Biodiversity Areas (IBA), which are important sites worldwide for bird conservation, following standardized quantitative criteria (Donald et al., 2019) (Table 5).

Table 5: Network of protected areas. Table lists the Protected Areas, Special Protection Areas, Sites of Community Importance, and Important Bird & Biodiversity Areas considered in the analysis.

Type of area	Designation	Code
Protected Areas (PA)		
	Parque Natural do Litoral Norte	PNLN
	Parque Natural da Arrábida	PNA
	Parque Natural do Sudoeste Alentejano e Costa Vicentina	PNSACV
	Reserva Natural das Dunas de São Jacinto	RNDSJ
	Reserva Natural das Berlengas	RNB
	Reserva Natural do Estuário do Tejo	RNET
	Reserva Natural do Estuário do Sado	RNES
	Reserva Natural das Lagoas de Santo André e da Sancha	RNLSAS
	Monumento Natural do Cabo Mondego	MNCM
Special Protection Areas (SPA)		
	Estuário dos Rios Minho e Coura	PTZPE0001
	Ria de Aveiro	PTZPE0004
	Ilhas Berlengas	PTZPE0009
	Lagoa de Santo André	PTZPE0013
	Lagoa da Sancha	PTZPE0014
	Costa Sudoeste	PTZPE0015
	Ria Formosa	PTZPE0017
	Cabo Espichel	PTZPE0050
	Aveiro/Nazaré	PTZPE0060
	Cabo Raso	PTZPE0061
Sites of Community Importance (SCI)		
	Estuário do Tejo	PTCON0009
	Arrábida/Espichel	PTCON0010
	Estuário do Sado	PTCON0011
	Estuário do Sado (extension under proposal)	
	Ria Formosa – Castro Marim	PTCON0013
	Litoral Norte	PTCON0017
	Peniche/Santa Cruz	PTCON0056
	Ria de Alvor	PTCON0058
	Ria de Aveiro	PTCON0061
	Maceda/Praia da Vieira	PTCON0063
	Costa de Setúbal (under proposal)	
Important Bird & Biodiversity Areas (IBA)		
	Aveiro-Nazaré	PTM01
	Berlengas	PTM02
	Cabo Raso	PTM03
	Ria Formosa	PTM04
	Cabo Espichel	PTM18
	Sagres	PTM20

4. Software

All analyses were conducted in R (R Core Team, 2023) using the packages *sf* (Pebesma, 2018) and *terra* (Hijmans, 2023). All figures were produced in *ggplot2* (Wickham, 2009). Base shapefiles were downloaded from ICNF geoCATALOGO¹⁰. The limits of wind farm proposed sites follow DGRM (2023b).

¹⁰ ICNF geoCATALOGO: <https://geocatalogo.icnf.pt/catalogo.html>

REFERENCES

- Akçakaya HR et al. 2018. Quantifying species recovery and conservation success to develop an IUCN Green List of Species. *Conservation Biology* **32**:1128–1138.
- Bernard A, Rodrigues ASL, Cazalis V, Grémillet D. 2021. Toward a global strategy for seabird tracking. *Conservation Letters* **14**:e12804.
- Best BD, Halpin PN. 2019. Minimizing wildlife impacts for offshore wind energy development: Winning tradeoffs for seabirds in space and cetaceans in time. *PLoS ONE* **14**:e0215722.
- Bird JP, Martin R, Akçakaya HR, Gilroy J, Burfield IJ, Garnett ST, Symes A, Taylor J, Şekercioğlu ÇH, Butchart SHM. 2020. Generation lengths of the world's birds and their implications for extinction risk. *Conservation Biology* **34**:1252–1261.
- BirdLife International. 2021. European Red List of Birds. Publications Office of the European Union, Luxemburg.
- BirdLife International 2023. IUCN Red List for birds. Downloaded from <http://datazone.birdlife.org> on 02/09/2023
- BirdLife International 2023. Seabird tracking database – Tracking ocean wanderers. <https://data.seabirdtracking.org>
- Bradbury G, Trinder M, Furness B, Banks AN, Caldow RWG, Hume D. 2014. Mapping Seabird Sensitivity to Offshore Wind Farms. *PLoS ONE* **9**:e106366.
- Brignon J-M, Lejart M, Nexer M, Michel S, Quentric A, Thiebaud L. 2022. A risk-based method to prioritize cumulative impacts assessment on marine biodiversity and research policy for offshore wind farms in France. *Environmental Science & Policy* **128**:264–276.
- Busch M, Garthe S. 2018. Looking at the bigger picture: the importance of considering annual cycles in impact assessments illustrated in a migratory seabird species. *ICES Journal of Marine Science* **75**:690–700.
- Cabral MJ, Almeida J, Almeida PR, Dellinger T, Ferrand de Almeida N, Oliveira ME, Palmeirim JM, Queirós AI, Rogado L, Santos-Reis M. 2005. Livro Vermelho dos Vertebrados de Portugal. Instituto da Conservação da Natureza.
- Carstensen J, Henriksen O, Teilmann J. 2006. Impacts of offshore wind farm construction on harbour porpoises: acoustic monitoring of echolocation activity using porpoise detectors (T-PODs). *Marine Ecology Progress Series* **321**:295–308.
- Catry P, Costa H, Elias G, Matias R. 2010. Aves de Portugal: Ornitologia do território continental. Assirio & Alwin.
- Certain G, Jørgensen LL, Christel I, Planque B, Bretagnolle V. 2015. Mapping the vulnerability of animal community to pressure in marine systems: disentangling pressure types and integrating their impact from the individual to the community level. *ICES Journal of Marine Science* **72**:1470–1482.
- Chen C, Jefferson TA, Chen B, Wang Y. 2022. Geographic range size, water temperature, and extrinsic threats predict the extinction risk in global cetaceans. *Global Change Biology* **28**:6541–6555.
- Clairbaux M, Jessopp M. 2021. Review of species-specific collision risks for sea birds. Deliverable D7.9 LC-SC3-RES-1–2019, X-rotor.
- Cook A, Johnston A, Wright L, Burton N. 2012. A review of flight heights and avoidance rates of birds in relation to offshore wind farms. Strategic Ornithological Support Services Project SOSS-02, BTO Research Report No. 618. BTO, Thetford. Available from <https://tethys.pnnl.gov/sites/default/files/publications/Cook-et-al-2012.pdf>.
- Cook ASCP, Humphreys EM, Bennet F, Masden EA, Burton NHK. 2018. Quantifying avian avoidance of offshore wind turbines: Current evidence and key knowledge gaps. *Marine Environmental Research* **140**:278–288.

- Cooke RSC, Eigenbrod F, Bates AE. 2019. Projected losses of global mammal and bird ecological strategies. *Nature Communications* **10**:2279.
- Correia AM, Gandra M, Liberal M, Valente R, Gil Á, Rosso M, Pierce GJ, Sousa-Pinto I. 2019. A dataset of cetacean occurrences in the Eastern North Atlantic. *Scientific Data* **6**:177.
- Courbin N, Besnard A, Boncourt E, Grémillet D. 2023. Flight heights of Scopoli's shearwaters *Calonectris diomedea* in the context of offshore wind farm developments. *bioRxiv preprint*. Available from <http://biorxiv.org/lookup/doi/10.1101/2023.05.14.540698> (accessed August 4, 2023).
- Critchley EJ, Grecian WJ, Kane A, Jessopp MJ, Quinn JL. 2018. Marine protected areas show low overlap with projected distributions of seabird populations in Britain and Ireland. *Biological Conservation* **224**:309–317.
- Cunningham E, Gamble A, Hart T, Humphreys E, Philip E, Tyler G, Wood M. 2022. The incursion of Highly Pathogenic Avian Influenza (HPAI) into North Atlantic seabird populations: an interim report from the 15th International Seabird Group conference. *Seabird Journal* **34**:67–73.
- Degraer S, Brabant R. 2009. Offshore wind farms in the Belgian part of the North Sea: State of the art after two years of environmental monitoring. Page 287. Royal Belgian Institute for Natural Sciences, Management Unit of the North Sea Mathematical Models. Marine ecosystem management unit. Available from https://odnature.naturalsciences.be/downloads/mumm/windfarms/monitoring_windmills_2009_final.pdf
- DGRM. 2023a. Proposta de Plano de Afetação para as Energias Renováveis Offshore. Page 77. Versão para Consulta Pública. DGRM - Direção-Geral de Recursos Naturais, Segurança e Serviços Marítimos. Available from https://participa.pt/contents/consultationdocument/Plano%20de%20Afeta%C3%A7%C3%A3o_PAER_Versao_CP_outubro.pdf (accessed October 20, 2023).
- DGRM. 2023b. Proposta de Plano de Afetação para as Energias Renováveis Offshore - ANEXO II Relatório de caracterização. Versão para Consulta Pública. DGRM - Direção-Geral de Recursos Naturais, Segurança e Serviços Marítimos. Available from https://participa.pt/contents/consultationdocument/ANEXO%20II_Relatorio_Characterizacao_PAER_Versao_CP_outubro.docx.pdf (accessed October 23, 2023).
- Dias MP, Martin R, Pearmain EJ, Burfield IJ, Small C, Phillips RA, Yates O, Lascelles B, Borboroglu PG, Croxall JP. 2019. Threats to seabirds: A global assessment. *Biological Conservation* **237**:525–537.
- Dierschke V, Furness RW, Garthe S. 2016. Seabirds and offshore wind farms in European waters: Avoidance and attraction. *Biological Conservation* **202**:59–68.
- Donald PF et al. 2019. Important Bird and Biodiversity Areas (IBAs): the development and characteristics of a global inventory of key sites for biodiversity. *Bird Conservation International* **29**:177–198. Cambridge University Press.
- Elmberg J, Hirschfeld E, Cardoso H, Hessel R. 2020. SEABIRD MIGRATION AT CABO CARVOEIRO (PENICHE, PORTUGAL) IN AUTUMN 2015.
- European Commission. 2021. The EU Blue Economy Report. Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg. Available from https://oceans-and-fisheries.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2021-05/the-eu-blue-economy-report-2021_en.pdf (accessed October 9, 2023).
- European Parliament. 2021. Draft Report on the Impact on the Fishing Sector of Offshore Windfarms and Other Renewable Energy Systems (2019/2158(INI)). Rapporteur: Peter van Dalen. EU. Committee on Fisheries. Available from https://www.europarl.europa.eu/doceo/document/PECH-PR-681090_EN.pdf (accessed October 9, 2023).
- Fliessbach KL, Borkenhagen K, Guse N, Markones N, Schwemmer P, Garthe S. 2019. A Ship Traffic Disturbance Vulnerability Index for Northwest European Seabirds as a Tool for Marine Spatial Planning. *Frontiers in Marine Science* **6**:192.

- Furness RW, Wade HM, Masden EA. 2013. Assessing vulnerability of marine bird populations to offshore wind farms. *Journal of Environmental Management* **119**:56–66.
- Garthe S, Hüppop O. 2004. Scaling possible adverse effects of marine wind farms on seabirds: developing and applying a vulnerability index: Marine wind farms and seabirds. *Journal of Applied Ecology* **41**:724–734.
- Garthe S, Markones N, Corman A-M. 2017. Possible impacts of offshore wind farms on seabirds: a pilot study in Northern Gannets in the southern North Sea. *Journal of Ornithology* **158**:345–349.
- Garthe S, Schwemmer H, Peschko V, Markones N, Müller S, Schwemmer P, Mercker M. 2023. Large-scale effects of offshore wind farms on seabirds of high conservation concern. *Scientific Reports* **13**:4779.
- Gauld JG et al. 2022. Hotspots in the grid: Avian sensitivity and vulnerability to collision risk from energy infrastructure interactions in Europe and North Africa. *Journal of Applied Ecology* **59**:1496–1512.
- Gielen D, Boshell F, Saygin D, Bazilian MD, Wagner N, Gorini R. 2019. The role of renewable energy in the global energy transformation. *Energy Strategy Reviews* **24**:38–50.
- Gill AB. 2005. Offshore renewable energy: ecological implications of generating electricity in the coastal zone. *Journal of Applied Ecology* **42**:605–615.
- Goodale MW, Milman A, Griffin CR. 2019. Assessing the cumulative adverse effects of offshore wind energy development on seabird foraging guilds along the East Coast of the United States. *Environmental Research Letters* **14**:074018. IOP Publishing.
- Granadeiro JP, Grade N, Lecoq M, Morais L, Santos C & Silva MC 1998. Breeding Madeiran Storm-petrels *Oceanodroma castro* on the Farilhões islands, Portugal. *Proceedings of the IV Mediterranean Seabird Symposium: Seabird Ecology and Coastal Zone Management in the Mediterranean*
- Grilo C et al. 2022. MAMMALS IN PORTUGAL: A data set of terrestrial, volant, and marine mammal occurrences in Portugal. *Ecology* **103**:e3654.
- Guilherme JL, Morais B, Alonso H, Dias MP. 2023. A dataset of seabird collision and displacement vulnerability factors relatively to marine wind farms in Portugal (Version 1). *Sociedade Portuguesa para o Estudo das Aves (SPEA)*.
- Halpern BS et al. 2015. Spatial and temporal changes in cumulative human impacts on the world's ocean. *Nature Communications* **6**:7615. Nature Publishing Group.
- Hijmans R 2023. *_terra: Spatial Data Analysis_*. R package version 1: 7-29.
<https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=terra>.
- iNaturalist 2023. Observations of cetaceans from mainland Portugal (up to 65km offshore) observed between 2001-2023. Exported from <https://www.inaturalist.org> on 07/09/2023.
- Johnston A, Cook ASCP, Wright LJ, Humphreys EM, Burton NHK. 2014. Modelling flight heights of marine birds to more accurately assess collision risk with offshore wind turbines. *Journal of Applied Ecology* **51**:31–41.
- Kelsey EC, Felis JJ, Czapanskiy M, Pereksta DM, Adams J. 2018. Collision and displacement vulnerability to offshore wind energy infrastructure among marine birds of the Pacific Outer Continental Shelf. *Journal of Environmental Management* **227**:229–247.
- Leopold MF, Boonman M, Collier MP, Davaasuren N, Fijn RC, Gyimesi A, de Jong J, Jongbloed RH, Jonge Poerink B, Kleyheeg-Hartman JC, Krijgsveld KL, Lagerveld S, Lensink R, Poot MJM, van der Wal JT, Scholl M 2014. A first approach to deal with cumulative effects on birds and bats of offshore wind farms and other human activities in the Southern North Sea. *IMARES Report C166/14*
- Lloret J, Turiel A, Solé J, Berdalet E, Sabatés A, Olivares A, Gili J-M, Vila-Subirós J, Sardá R. 2022. Unravelling the ecological impacts of large-scale offshore wind farms in the Mediterranean Sea. *Science of The Total Environment* **824**:153803.

- Madsen P, Wahlberg M, Tougaard J, Lucke K, Tyack P. 2006. Wind turbine underwater noise and marine mammals: implications of current knowledge and data needs. *Marine Ecology Progress Series* **309**:279–295.
- Masden EA, Haydon DT, Fox AD, Furness RW, Bullman R, Desholm M. 2009. Barriers to movement: impacts of wind farms on migrating birds. *ICES Journal of Marine Science* **66**:746–753.
- Meirinho A, Barros N, Oliveira N, Catry P, Lecoq M, Paiva VH, Geraldés P, Granadeiro JP, Ramirez I, Andrade J. 2014. Atlas das Aves Marinhas de Portugal. Sociedade Portuguesa para o Estudo das Aves, LabOr- Laboratório de Ornitologia – ICAAM - Universidade de Évora, Instituto da Conservação da Natureza e das Florestas, Instituto das Florestas e Conservação da Natureza (Madeira), Secretaria Regional da Energia, Ambiente e Turismo (Açores) e Associação Portuguesa de Anilhadores de Aves, Lisboa. Available from http://www.atlasavesmarinhas.pt/assets/pdf/atlas_aves_marinhas_alta_resolucao.pdf (accessed July 24, 2023).
- Oliveira N et al. 2015. Seabird bycatch in Portuguese mainland coastal fisheries: An assessment through on-board observations and fishermen interviews. *Global Ecology and Conservation* **3**:51–61.
- Paton P, Winiarski K, Trocki C, McWilliams S. 2010. Interim Technical Report for the Rhode Island Ocean Special Area Management Plan 2010. Technical Report.
- Pebesma E. 2018. Simple Features for R: Standardized Support for Spatial Vector Data. *The R Journal* **10**:439.
- Peschko V, Mendel B, Müller S, Markones N, Mercker M, Garthe S. 2020. Effects of offshore windfarms on seabird abundance: Strong effects in spring and in the breeding season. *Marine Environmental Research* **162**:105157.
- Plazas-Jiménez D, Cianciaruso MV. 2020. Valuing Ecosystem Services Can Help to Save Seabirds. *Trends in Ecology & Evolution* **35**:757–762.
- R Core Team. 2023. R: A Language and Environment for Statistical Computing. R Foundation for Statistical Computing, Vienna, Austria. Available from <https://www.R-project.org/>.
- Reid K, Baker GB, Woehler EJ. 2023. An ecological risk assessment for the impacts of offshore wind farms on birds in Australia. *Austral Ecology* **48**:418–439.
- Richards C, Cooke RSC, Bates AE. 2020. Biological traits of seabirds predict extinction risk and vulnerability to anthropogenic threats. preprint. *Ecology*. Available from <http://biorxiv.org/lookup/doi/10.1101/2020.09.30.321513> (accessed November 5, 2020).
- Rodríguez A et al. 2019. Future Directions in Conservation Research on Petrels and Shearwaters. *Frontiers in Marine Science* **6**. Available from <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fmars.2019.00094> (accessed October 24, 2023).
- Rogalla S, Nicolai MPJ, Porchetta S, Glabeke G, Battistella C, D’Alba L, Gianneschi NC, Van Beeck J, Shawkey MD. 2021. The evolution of darker wings in seabirds in relation to temperature-dependent flight efficiency. *Journal of The Royal Society Interface* **18**:20210236.
- Schwemmer P et al. 2023. Behavioral responses to offshore windfarms during migration of a declining shorebird species revealed by GPS-telemetry. *Journal of Environmental Management* **342**:118131.
- Serratos J, Allinson T. 2022. AVISTEP: the Avian Sensitivity Tool for Energy Planning. Technical Manual. BidLife International, Cambridge, UK.
- Signa G, Mazzola A, Vizzini S. 2021. Seabird influence on ecological processes in coastal marine ecosystems: An overlooked role? A critical review. *Estuarine, Coastal and Shelf Science* **250**:107164.
- Soanes LM, Bright JA, Angel LP, Arnould JPY, Bolton M, Berlincourt M, Lascelles B, Owen E, Simon-Bouhet B, Green JA. 2016. Defining marine important bird areas: Testing the foraging radius approach. *Biological Conservation* **196**:69–79.

- Stone CJ, Webb A, Barton C, Ratcliffe N, Reed TC, Tasker ML, Camphuysen CJ, Pienkowski MW. 1995. An atlas of seabird distribution in north-west European waters. JNCC, Peterborough, UK.
- Sutherland WJ et al. 2012. A horizon scanning assessment of current and potential future threats to migratory shorebirds. *Ibis* **154**:663–679.
- Thompson PM, Lusseau D, Barton T, Simmons D, Rusin J, Bailey H. 2010. Assessing the responses of coastal cetaceans to the construction of offshore wind turbines. *Marine Pollution Bulletin* **60**:1200–1208.
- Tobias JA et al. 2022. AVONET: morphological, ecological and geographical data for all birds. *Ecology Letters* **25**:581–597.
- Travers MS. 2023. Chapter 14 - Reducing collisions with structures. Pages 379–401 in Young L, VanderWerf E, editors. *Conservation of Marine Birds*. Academic Press. Available from <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/B9780323885393000042> (accessed October 22, 2023).
- UNEP/CMS. 2018. Agreement on the Conservation of African-Eurasian Migratory Waterbirds (AEWA). Convention on the Conservation of Migratory Species of Wild Animals (CMS), Durban, South Africa. Available from https://www.unep-aewa.org/sites/default/files/basic_page_documents/agreement_text_english_final.pdf.
- Vingada J et al. 2011. SafeSea - Manual de apoio para a promoção de uma pesca mais sustentável e de um mar seguro para cetáceos. Programa EEAGrants - EEA Financial Mechanism 2004-2009 (Projecto 0039):114.
- Virtanen EA, Lappalainen J, Nurmi M, Viitasalo M, Tikanmäki M, Heinonen J, Atlaskin E, Kallasvuo M, Tikkanen H, Moilanen A. 2022. Balancing profitability of energy production, societal impacts and biodiversity in offshore wind farm design. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* **158**:112087.
- Wade HM, Masden EA, Jackson AC, Furness RW. 2016. Incorporating data uncertainty when estimating potential vulnerability of Scottish seabirds to marine renewable energy developments. *Marine Policy* **70**:108–113.
- Watts BD, Hines C, Duval L, Wilke AL. 2022. Exposure of Whimbrels to offshore wind leases during departure from and arrival to a major mid-Atlantic staging site. *Avian Conservation and Ecology* **17**:art31.
- Wickham H. 2009. *ggplot2: Elegant Graphics for Data Analysis*. Springer-Verlag, New York. Available from <https://www.springer.com/gp/book/9780387981413> (accessed May 10, 2021).
- Wikelski M, Davidson SC, Kays RW. 2023. Movebank: archive, analysis and sharing of animal movement data. Hosted by the Max Planck Institute of Animal Behavior. Available from www.movebank.org.
- Willmot JR, Forcey G, Kent A. 2013. The Relative Vulnerability of Migratory Bird Species to Offshore Wind Energy Projects on the Atlantic Outer Continental Shelf: An Assessment Method and Database. OCS Study BOEM 2013-207. U.S. Department of the Interior, Bureau of Ocean Energy Management, Office of Renewable Energy Programs, Herndon, VA. Available from <https://espis.boem.gov/final%20reports/5319.pdf>.

ANNEX I

Maps of seabird sensitivity to collision (i.e., Collision Sensitivity Index – CSI) and sensitivity to displacement (i.e., Displacement Sensitivity Index – DSI).

Figure S1: Seabird sensitivity to collision and sensitivity to displacement. Seabird sensitivity to collision with, and displacement due to disturbance from, marine wind farm expansion in Portugal was calculated using density-distribution maps (ind.s per 4x4 km grid cells) across the seasons of the year each species occurs in Portugal (Meirinho et al., 2014), and a **(a)** Collision Sensitivity Index (CSI) and a **(b)** Displacement Sensitivity Index (DSI). For each of the 34 species, we multiplied the natural log of the density in each grid cell by the respective CSI or DSI value. The final maps were obtained by summing the values in each cell across species (see Methods). Isolines delineate five categories of sensitivity: low (dark blue) to very high (dark red). Boundaries of proposed wind farm sites are in white (the Aguçadora site is a pilot marine wind farm in operation since 2020).